

D5.1:

Responsible Research and Innovation approach for transitioning
the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories

Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Deliverable Title: D5.1 Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Work Package: Implementation and Improvement
V1.0

Lead beneficiary: The Paper Province Ekonomisk Foerening, PP

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Document information

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Description of the deliverable (3-5 lines)	As a result of previous work in the project (Visioning, Roadmapping, and Action Plans) this document reports on the implementation of the chosen actions within the project period till project month 30 (with the start of the possibility for implementing actions developed inside this project by months 21 (Oct. 2021).
Key words	Actions bridging the gaps; roadmap goals; affected stakeholders; addressed roadmap domains.

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D5.1 – Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Executive summary

DigiTeRRI elaborates a framework for the transition of three industry regions in Austria (Styria), in France (Grand Est), and in Sweden (Värmland) into digitalised R&I ecosystems. With point of departure in the specific characteristics of each territory an RRI approach (also addressing gender equality, science education, open access/open data, public engagement, and ethics) has been used to create transparency and inclusiveness for the stakeholders involved in the change. Prior in the project each territory has developed a vision statement for this transition followed by the construction of roadmaps with specific goals and objectives. Based on the developed objectives and identified gaps, actions for reaching these objectives have been developed. The project plan foresees that each DigiTeRRI territory implements already 12 actions during the project period. 9 of these 12 actions are planned to be implemented till project month 30 (June 2022) and the remaining 3 actions are implemented till the end of the project (project month 36 by end Dec 2022). From the roadmap each territory has put together an action plan with 12 (9+3) actions to be implemented during a 15-month period within the timeframe of project. The actions have been chosen to support a RRI approach and with respect to territorial change.

This deliverable D5.1 describes the management of the implementation of the actions within the project period M21-M30. An implementation team was formed with an assigned implementation coordinator for each territory. To support this team a monitoring tool was developed and used. The implementation team had monthly update meetings to track the development in the implementation process.

Deliverable D5.1 also summarizes information for each implemented action in all three territories using the same structure enabling comparison between the territories. In the beginning of the presentation of each territory there is also a graphical display showing the timeline for the implementation process for each territory.

1. Introduction and Background

The DigiTeRRI project is developing a framework and roadmap for a responsible transition of traditional industrial regions into digitalised industrial self-sustaining R&I ecosystems using the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach. Based on the stocktaking and mapping (D2.3 and D2.4), The co-creation of the framework (D2.1), the mapping of the territories (D2.3), the Visioning vision statement (D3.3), and the Roadmap itself with defined goals, objectives, and gaps ping process (D4.2), the actions for bridging the gaps and reaching the objectives were developed (D4.3). The work was done with project partners and their stakeholders from three regions in Europe, Värmland in Sweden, Region Grand Est in France, and Steiermark in Austria, (Figure 1). The project addresses the complexity of challenges in the interaction of science, economy, government, and society in the defined territories. Multi-stakeholders from the three partner territories are involved in this project.

This deliverable D5.1 is the documentation of the actions implemented in Phase D of the DigiTeRRI roadmap process (see Figure 1). This report gives the current situation (project month 30) about the implementation process. Most of the 12 planned actions in each territory are already implemented. Few are still ongoing and will be reported in the final report. The report covers the actions that has been implemented during project month M21-M30. on the implementation of at least 9+3 actions each territory has selected from the roadmap (phase C). The 9+3 actions to focus on in a 15-month period. The actions has been chosen to support a RRI approach with respect to territorial change. The report covers the actions that has been implemented during project month M21-M30. They are presented in detail each territory at a time.

Figure 1: Scheme of strategic roadmapping in DigiTeRRI

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2. Management and Monitoring of the implementation process

A planning work preceded the implementation process to understand the connection between the action plans (D4.3), implementing the actions (T5.1), monitoring the implementation (T5.2), and evaluating the framework and measures (T5.3). This work resulted in insights what information needed to be collected prior to, during, and after the execution of each action.

With a lot of actions taking place in the three territories in parallel and the amount of information to be collected for each action there was a need for an easy-to-use monitoring tool to track the progress of the implementation of the actions. With the help and support from WeDo (project partner no. 4) we developed a monitoring tool using Smartsheet™. The Smartsheet fulfils several purposes. It consists of two different components, Dashboard and Data Grid.

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Figure 2: Smartsheet – Dashboard

Figure 2 gives an overview about the implementation situation on a specific time point in each of the three DigiTeRRI territories.

The dashboards are graphical compilations of the status of the implementation of the actions in each territory, see Figure 2. The dashboards present the progress as pie charts with the following colour code; Blue = Not started, Yellow = In progress, Green = Finished, and Red = Delayed. In the dashboard section there are also staple diagrams showing the progress of every action in percentage from 0-100%. For further information see the appendix.

In the Data Grid component, Figure 3, all vital planning for each action was collected. Information from the data grids is presented in detail later in this report. In the Data Grid we also added persons responsible for one or several actions in each territory, the action managers. If an action was overdue the responsible action manager received an automatically generated notification e-mail. In this e-mail the action manager was asked to explain the reason for the delay, and adjustments that was taken to correct for the delay.

	Action Title	Kind of action	Starting date	Dead line date	Assigned to
1	Apply the competence wheel	Team meeting	10/01/21	12/31/21	Mikael Holmgren, Per Myhrén
2	Use the competence wheel	Discussion forum	10/01/21	06/30/22	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhren@paperprovince.com
3	Mapping of solutions in use	Study	10/01/21	03/31/22	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhren@paperprovince.com
4	Survey on the future needs	Study	10/01/21	03/31/22	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhren@paperprovince.com
5	Design offers and services	Workshop	02/01/22	12/31/22	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhren@paperprovince.com
6	Digital Data Stewardship Course	Training	01/01/22	09/30/22	eamonn.mccallion@kau.se, James Lees, Sofia Andersson
7	Territorial attractiveness of Värmland	Stakeholder integration	02/01/22	12/31/22	Angelica Jacobo, Eamonn McCallion, helen.vogelmann@re
8	Digitalisation and RRI in Leadershi	Training	11/01/21	09/30/22	eamonn.mccallion@kau.se
9	Compilation of analytical reports at	Study	10/01/21	06/30/22	Anders Olsson, Angelica Jacobo, helen.vogelmann@regior
10	Hiring of digital coordinator	Recruitment	10/01/21	12/31/21	Anders Olsson, helen.vogelmann@regionvarmland.se
11	Digitalisation and S3	Stakeholder integration	10/01/21	03/31/22	Anders Olsson, Angelica Jacobo, helen.vogelmann@regior

Figure 3: Smartsheet – Data Grid

Each territory selected a coordinator to keep track on the implementation process. The coordinators also had ongoing dialogues with the action managers in their territory.

First Monday in every month there was an update meeting. In these meetings the territory coordinators, task leader for of T5.2, and WeDo participated and on occasions also AIT (DigiTeRRI coordinator). On the agenda there was a status report from each territory followed by general discussions about the ongoing implementation process. As a result of these discussions a template for an action report was produced to provide complementary information about the finished actions. These reports were attached in the Smartsheet tool.

During a project meeting in Värmland, May 23rd -25th 2022, in Värmland there was a discussion related to cross territory learning/experience exchanges, valuable for the rest of the implementation process. Some of the learnings

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where challenges related to Covid pandemic but also how to keep up the stakeholder engagement over time when there is a timespan between the different actions, we wanted the different stakeholders to participate in.

In the following sections there are presentations of the implemented actions in each territory with a focus in this report on the implemented actions until June 30th. In addition, there are also some brief information on the actions that are ongoing but will be completed later in the project outside the scope of this report.

The sections start with information on the regional management followed by a timeline and detailed information on each action. The implemented actions build the basis for monitoring and describing the changes regarding the DigiTeRRI project objectives, the transition into a digitalised regions and implementing RRI.

In the following sections there are presentations of the implemented actions in each territory with a focus in this report on the implemented actions until June 30th. In addition, there are also some brief information on the actions that are ongoing but will be completed later in the project outside the scope of this report. The sections start with information on the regional management followed by a timeline and detailed information on each action.

The implemented actions build the basis for monitoring and describing the changes regarding the DigiTeRRI project objectives, the transition into a digitalised regions and implementing RRI.

3. Implementation process in the three territories

3.1 Implementation Process - Värmland

The management of the implementation process of the actions in Värmland was taken care of by the three DigiTeRRI Värmland partners in the project, Paper Province (PP), Karlstad University (KAU) and Region Värmland (Värmland) and in close cooperation with Compare, an important stakeholder. The assigned action managers for each action belong to these organizations.

The Värmland team were divided in three sub-groups. Paper Province and Compare were responsible for the planning and the execution of the actions aimed at the business/industry sector (actions #1-5). KAU was responsible for actions aimed at the academia/government/industry (action #6, 8 and 13). Region Värmland was responsible for actions #7, 9-12).

Originally in the developed action plan 14 actions were defined. Due to domestic difficulties within the student union at Karlstad university action #13 Interaction and exchange with other student unions had to be cancelled for the project period, although the first contacts are already developed.

Every week the Värmland team had an update meeting with discussions on the project and the status on the implementation process.

Actions within the project but outside the timeframe of this report are:

Action #5 Design offers and services Action #6 Digital Data Stewardship Course, Action #7 Territorial attractiveness of Värmland, Action #8 Digitalisation and RRI in Leadership Training. Action#5 and 7 deviate from the original plan with an estimated end date in late Q4 2022. There are several reasons for this timeline shift. The good news is that the actions have not changed, and the regional actors engaged in designing the actions feel they are solid and still relevant. However, the main causes for the deviation in the time frame is the rush of events once in person meetings became possible post COVID pandemic, calendar priorities for staff between core business and external development events alongside the engagement of actors that have to focus on their organisational needs both in the increased demand for services and production.

Name	M21 Sep 21	M22 Oct 21	M23 Nov 21	M24 Dec 21	M25 Jan 22	M26 Feb 22	M27 Mar 22	M28 Apr 22	M29 May 22	M30 Jun 22*	M31 Jul 22	M32 Aug 22	M33 Sep 22	M34 Oct 22	M35 Nov 22	M36 Dec 22
Apply the competence wheel																
Use the competence wheel																
Mapping of solutions in use																
Survey on the future needs																
Design offers and services																
Digital Data Stewardship Course																
Territorial attractiveness of Värmland																
Digitalisation and RRI in Leadership Training																
Compilation of analytical reports and studies																
Hiring of digital coordinator																
Digitalisation and S3																
Digitalisation and S3 - expansion to Dalarna																
Incubator exchange																

M21-M32: 9 implemented actions

M33-M36: Additional 3 implemented actions

*Due date implementation report

Figure 4: Time implementation of actions in Värmland

3.1.1 Action #1 - Apply the competence wheel

Name (kind) of action: Team meetings

Status: Completed

Start: starting in October 2021

Duration: Q4 2021

Finish: December 2021

Location: Digital meetings

Description of the action: A well proven methodology called Competence Wheel was presented for companies in the region as a tool to be used to identify the competence gap as well as the future needs from the industry and the possibilities that are coming with new technology.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: The primary target groups were companies in the region (the companies in the Digitalization network)

Number of participants: 7

Communication/PR activities: E-mail correspondence from Paper Province/ Compare to the member companies in the Digitalization network.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: This activity belongs to the roadmap domain Knowledge and skills. The goal is High level data management courses.

Which gap will be closed with this action? Low data management capabilities and capacities on high level data science management currently.

Action result/-s: Formation of a regional digitalization network.

Which effect do you anticipate? Open and deepen the dialogue between the companies in the region and Karlstad university /other education providers.

Responsible organisation/actor: The Värmland team (Per Myhrén, Paper Province and Mikael Holmgren, Compare)

Planning and organisation of the action: Paper Province and Compare are coordinating regional companies with focus on digitalisation and industrial automation. In dialogues with these (core) companies we set the foundation for the rest of the companies in the region.

3.1.2 Action #2 - Use competence-wheel to investigate the needs of open data and data science within companies

Name (kind) of action: Discussion forums

Status: Completed

Date and location: Q4 2021 starting in November

Finish: Q1 2022

Description of the action: Initial discussions with, Cluster, Academia, education provider and companies to identify the needs from the industry. The academia and education providers presented the content in their courses and industry will presented the competence gap they have. This action is also part of action #4.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry and Business

Number of participants: 11

Communication/PR activities: Paper Province and Compare communicate with the different stakeholders to invite for both physical and digital meetings.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: This activity belongs to the roadmap domain Knowledge and skills. The goal is High level data management courses.

Which gap will be closed with this action? Low data management capabilities and capacities on high level data science management.

Action result/-s: A foundation for the mapping needs and solutions (action #3).

Which effect do you anticipate? Development of data management courses based on the needs in the industry.

Responsible organisation/actor: Per Myhrén, Paper Province and Mikael Holmgren, Compare

Planning and organisation of the action:In meetings discussions were held to pick relevant questions to be used in a survey as part of the mapping of needs.

3.1.3 Action #3 - Mapping of solutions in use

Name (kind) of action: Discussion forum and study

Status: Completed

Date and location: Q4 2021, Digitally Teams meetings

Finish: Q1 2022

Description of the action: Discussing the full battery of questions in the Competence wheel and sort out the relevant questions for mapping which solutions of technical knowledge are in use today. This action is part of action #4.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Business

Number of participants: 7

Communication/PR activities: Marketing of the purpose and get the business interested to participate.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: This activity belongs to the roadmap domain Technology/Develop methods and tools for instructions and manuals with digital technics.

Which gap will be closed with this action? Digital technics are used in smaller scales and there is a lack of coordination between companies which hinders efficient implementation. Get a mutual understanding of which solutions the companies are using today. Use this knowledge to address relevant questions for action#4.

Action result/-s: A re-worked questionnaire for distribution to the business/industry stakeholders in Värmland.

Which effect do you anticipate? Mutual understanding of all kinds of solutions in use already today and possibilities to share.

Responsible organisation/actor: Per Myhrén, Paper Province and Mikael Holmgren, Compare

Planning and organisation of the action: Meetings with companies and Academia to discuss the solution in use today and needs for the future. The results from the meetings provide information for action #4.

3.1.4 Action #4 -Survey for the future needs

Name (kind) of action: Survey of the future needs of data management knowledge and technical solutions.

Status: Completed

Date and location: January 2022, digitally

Finish: Q1 2022

Description of the action: Using a set of questions from the Competence wheel and the insights as results of actions#1-3 to construct a web-based questionnaire. The survey maps the future needs of Data management courses and technical solutions to be able to develop offers and services that meet the needs.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Business

Number of participants: 71 stakeholders received the questionnaire (13 replied)

Communication/PR activities: Through e-mails from Paper Province and Compare 71 stakeholders were invited to participate in the survey. The communication to participate in the survey were also communicated in network meetings.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: This activity belongs to the roadmap domains Knowledge and skills, the goal is High level data management courses and Technology/Develop methods and tools for instructions and manuals with digital technics.

Which gap will be closed with this action? The lack of knowledge of the future needs of digital competence and technical solutions in the companies of the region.

Action result/-s: The result from the survey will be the point of departure in the workshop in action #5.

Which effect do you anticipate? Increased digital competence in the region and increased cooperation on technical solutions between companies.

Responsible organisation/actor: Per Myhrén, Paper Province and Angelica Jacobo, Compare

Planning and organisation of the action: Paper Province and Compare modified the questionnaire in the Competence wheel and put it in Microsoft Forms. The questionnaire was sent out Feb. 10th with a reminder on Feb. 25th.

3.1.5 Action #5 - Design offers and services

Name (kind) of action: Workshop-s

Status: Ongoing

Date and location: Q2 2022, physical workshop at Karlstad Innovation Park

Finish: Dec. 31th 2022

Description of the action: The first workshop is scheduled Sep. 15th.

3.1.6 Action #6 - Digital Data Stewardship Course

Name (kind) of action: Training

Status: Ongoing

Date and location: Q1 2022

Finish: 2022-09-30

Description of the action: Provide a data stewardship course for researchers, public bodies, and business sector.

3.1.7 Action #7 - Territorial attractiveness of Värmland

Name (kind) of action: Stakeholder integration

Status: Ongoing

Date and location: February 2022, digital and physical

Finish: December 2022

Description of the action: Territorial attractiveness of Värmland, and that as part of the further internationalisation of Värmland based business. A hybrid conference on RRI and digitalization.

3.1.8 Action #8 - Digitalisation and RRI in Leadership Training

Name (kind) of action: Training

Status: Ongoing

Date and location: November 2021, digital and physical

Finish: Q3 2022

Description of the action: Provide a data leadership course for researchers, public bodies, and business sector.

3.1.9 Action #9 – Compilation of analytical reports and studies

Name (kind) of action: Study

Status: Completed

Date and location: October 2021, digitally

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: Compilation of findings of reports and studies. Draw conclusions on the digital divide, social contract, and the effects on citizenship in the context of citizenship through RRI lenses.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Academia, Government, Society, Education research

Number of participants: 0, desktop study as knowledge input to sustainable smart specialisation process in North Middle Sweden (Värmland, Dalarna and Gävleborg).

Communication/PR activities: In order to spread the information from this compilation we will have presentations for politicians and development responsible employees in Region Värmland.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Knowledge & skills. The overarching goal is to identify studies and organisations that can analyse DMA.

Which gap will be closed with this action? Region Värmland has identified severe gaps in the socioeconomic study 2020. The gaps are educational, generational, gender, age, migration, and geography related. The gaps in different reports and analyses need to be compiled and from them different actions derived.

Action result/-s: A compilation of reports and studies as well supporting national organisations.

Which effect do you anticipate? Baseline and compilation of matureness of DMA.

Responsible organisation/actor: Regional development department of Region Värmland.

Planning and organisation of the action: Discussion with the new digital coordinator in Värmland on how a regional roadmap for Värmland could be designed.

3.1.10 Action #10 - Hiring of digital coordinator

Name (kind) of action: Recruitment

Status: Completed

Date and location: October 2021, digital

Finish: December 2021

Description of the action: Hiring regional digital coordinator and transfer knowledge and incorporate the expert into the DigiTeRRI work.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Academia, Government, Society, Education research

Number of participants: 4

Communication/PR activities: Recruitment advertisement

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Knowledge & skills, networks, and collaboration. The overarching goal is to enhance the competence and capacity of Region Värmland and to interact in the networks that are connected to sustainable smart specialisation.

Which gap will be closed with this action? Region Värmland has identified severe gaps in the socioeconomic study 2020. The gaps are educational, generational, gender, age, migration, and geography related.

Action result/-s: Recruitment of Angelica Jacobo

Which effect do you anticipate? Region Värmland has identified severe gaps in the socioeconomic study 2020. The gaps are educational, generational, gender, age, migration, and geography related. The gaps in different reports and analyses need to be compiled and from them different actions derived.

Responsible organisation/actor: Regional development department of Region Värmland.

Planning and organisation of the action: Based on the Swedish agency for growth Tillväxtverket as well as the Swedish Government support financially in designing the profile of the recruitment.

3.1.11 Action #11 – Digitalisation and S3

Name (kind) of action: Stakeholder integration

Status: Completed

Date and location: October 2021, digital

Finish: Q1 2022

Description of the action: Working with the regional steering groups, civil servants, and politicians to ensure the horizontal theme of digitalisation is informed by the DigiTeRRI project and embedded into the relevant strategies.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Academia, Government, Society, Education research

Number of participants: 45

Communication/PR activities: Invitation to the workshop 3 and discussions on how DigiTeRRI can contribute to the sustainable smart specialisation strategy.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Network & collaboration. Introduce the action to a public organisation's and receive feedback to incorporate into the future implementation of the sustainable smart specialisation strategy.

Which gap will be closed with this action? Region Värmland has identified severe gaps in the socioeconomic study 2020. The gaps are educational, generational, gender, age, migration, and geography related.

Action result/-s: Introduce the action to a public organisation's and receive feedback to incorporate into the future implementation of the sustainable smart specialisation strategy.

Which effect do you anticipate? Impact on the sustainable smart specialisation strategy that could lead to a roadmap for digitalisation for the public sector and its services.

Responsible organisation/actor: Regional development department of Region Värmland.

Planning and organisation of the action: Planned together with the senior expert Research and Innovation at Region Värmland.

3.1.12 Action #12 - Digitalisation and S3 – Expansion to Dalarna

Name (kind) of action: Stakeholder integration

Status: Completed

Date and location: October 2021, digital

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: Working with the regional actors within the regional governance framework in Dalarna to design and deliver a DigiTeRRI light that will contribute to their smart specialisation strategy.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Academia, Government, Society, Education research.

Number of participants: 65

Communication/PR activities: Region Dalarna & Värmland, the outputs from DigiTeRRI will be transferred to clusters, politicians, and officials in Region Dalarna during a transfer workshop.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Network & collaboration. Overarching goal to transfer knowledge of the process of DigiTeRRI, introduce the methodology and the learnings to conduct process in Dalarna fall 2022.

Which gap will be closed with this action? Region Dalarna has identified severe gaps in the socioeconomic study 2020. The gaps are educational, generational, gender, age, migration, and geography related.

Action result/-s: Transfer of methodology and incorporated into a project to be executed start 1st of July 2022.

Which effect do you anticipate? DigiTeRRI Roadmap light in Dalarna as well as horizontal platform in the new sustainable smart specialisation strategy of Dalarna.

Responsible organisation/actor: Regional development department of Region Värmland.

Planning and organisation of the action: 6 meetings with Region Dalarna, presentation to all innovation eco-system actors as well as feedback workshop with Region Dalarna and Region Gävleborg.

3.1.13 Action #13 - Incubator exchange (lead partner Styria action#9)

Name (kind) of action: Discussion forum

Status: Completed

Date and location: Q2 2022, digital

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: Develop digital awareness programs and encourage potential founders of their own start-up in a digital environment. Network interface between entrepreneurs with compatible interests and promote or support international market expansion efforts. Promoting digital processes in business management and technical cooperation between companies or expanding digital opportunities to ensure the economic strength of the regions. The cross regional Incubator network supports the development of the digital transformation of the regions through their collaboration and elaboration of risks & opportunities for young companies regarding sustainable growth strategies.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Business

Number of participants: 10

Communication/PR activities: Franz Edler, Centre of Applied Technology

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives:
Leadership, business & market, network and collaboration

Which gap will be closed with this action? The gap of extensive possibility for interaction of incubators.

Action result/-s: Increased knowledge/training for participation on digital fair and international exposure for 4 Startup companies in Värmland.

Which effect do you anticipate? Platform for Networking.

Responsible organisation/actor: Franz Edler, Centre of Applied Technology.

Planning and organisation of the action: Franz Edler, Centre of Applied Technology.

3.2 Implementation Process – Styria

In the action plan drawn up by the Styrian project team, the contents, and timetables for the implementation of the actions were developed. An additional person was nominated for each action. Managers for all actions come from Montanuniversität Leoben, Center of Applied Technology, and the Municipality Bruck/Mur. The action plan also defined the timetable for the implementation of the actions.

The regional coordinator organised regular meetings where the project team and the other responsible action managers exchanged information and discussed the progress of the actions and their interaction. The networking of actions was seen as having great potential. Linked actions helped to address more stakeholders. Stakeholders had the advantage of being more fully informed and getting a broader perspective of this transition & RRI approach. They were thus able to participate on many actions at the same time.

The regional organiser was also involved in the regular meetings of the overall project team. The meetings were held at the beginning of each month. For these coordination meetings, the progress of the Styrian measure implementation was entered into the "Smartsheet" monitoring software so that all activities could be made transparent for the other project participants. The meetings were also used to inform project partners from the other territories about supra-regional actions and to involve them in the preparation.

Originally in the developed action plan 15 actions were planned. At the beginning of the implementation phase the Styrian project team prioritised them according to the available budget resource and urgency. Actions which offered a networking with the other territories aiming to reaching a sustainable cooperation after the DigiTeRRI project were ranked very highly. Initiatives under the responsibility of stakeholders were also selected because for a better grounding of the roadmap process in the territory.

As can be seen from the timetable, the Styrian team planned most of the action in the period between the period between June 2021 and November 2022. Most of the actions can be finished before the planned deadlines. In the time planning for almost all actions a time puffer was included because in 2021 when doing the action planning COVID gave several uncertainties. The Styrian project team managed to complete most of the planned 12 actions by the end of June 2022. One action is still pending - "Fit4MINT" and

will be finished till the last quarter of 2022. Action#5 Digital Lab make good progress and will be finished by end of October.

One action within the project but outside the timeframe for this report is:

Action #3 Fit4MINT (see Action Plan of DigiTeRRI, D4.3).

Optional action #2 Exchange of knowledge on digitalisation is still under consideration for implementation. Action #15 Cultural Exchange will not be implemented because the cross territorial events by web are not so likely because stakeholder are indicated of been tiered in social isolation. Action #15 Cultural exchange will not be implemented as cross-territorial action because events on the internet are no longer as likely after Corona, as stakeholders are more likely to want to have cultural events more in the physical world aiming to escape social isolation.

Name	M21 Sep 21	M22 Oct 21	M23 Nov 21	M24 Dec 21	M25 Jan 22	M26 Feb 22	M27 Mar 22	M28 Apr 22	M29 May 22	M30 Jun 22*	M31 Jul 22	M32 Aug 22	M33 Sep 22	M34 Oct 22	M35 Nov 22	M36 Dec 22
Blackout precautions																
Females fit for digitalisation																
Fit4MINT																
Exchange of Student Unions																
Design offers and services																
Digi@Lab																
Awareness of the Styrian Roadmap																
Concept development "Styria Universal platform"																
Incubator exchange for fostering entrepreneurship in digitalisation																
Cross Regional Event - B2B Networking event on industry and digitalisation																
Plan Scan&Shop - explore the regional economy and important facilities online																
Job platform for municipality co-workers																

M21-M32: 9 implemented actions

M33-M36-Additional 3 implemented actions

*Due date implementation report

Figure 5: Time implementation of actions in Styria

3.2.1 Action #1 – Blackout precautions

Name (kind) of action: Concept development of a precaution master plan, information material for the public

Status: Completed

Date and location: Start in January 2022, online and physical meetings, and workshops

Finish: Q2 2022

Description of the action: The threat of a “blackout” of the energy supply and the associated consequences for communities, the economy and the population seem to be a central issue for the future. A completely break-down of energy supply is a serious situation for a digitalised society. In addition to the digital basic supply, this also applies to the decentralized energy supply (to secure basic needs). While larger cities, companies and infrastructure providers are already well prepared here, further support for smaller communities and businesses is required, as well as, of course, comprehensive information for the population. Building on existing knowledge, a broad awareness and information campaign is to be implemented in order to provide information as extensively and widely as possible. Aim is to increase the resilience against blackout and have stable and robust environment for digitalisation.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, business, government, public

Number of participants: 5

Communication/PR activities: Invitation in the dialog of regional companies and municipalities

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Infrastructure, Technology

Which gap will be closed with this action? Creation of an information platform, (digital and personal) about the risks associated with a “blackout” and the necessary prerequisites for the best possible management.

Action result/-s: A current situation analysis on the ability to handle a blackout situation in Bruck an der Mur, Blackout precaution master plan.

Which effect do you anticipate? Anticipation of future developments, responsiveness action to secure the energy supply of the public and society in the territory.

Responsible organisation/actor: Eric Weber, Standort Marketing Bruck an der Mur

Planning and organisation of the action: Standort Marketing Bruck an der Mur is organising this event.

3.2.2 Action #2 - Females fit for digitalisation

Name (kind) of action: Discussion forum and creating awareness, networking, and exchange

Status: Completed

Start: Start in October 2021, Online / Web Montanuniversitaet – Study of state of the art in Styria and cross regional exchange with the project partner and their activities (e.g. Gender and Girls workshop in Mulhouse, translation of app for quiz for young girls to German language).

Finish: March 2022

Description of the action: The topic of gender equality was seen as an important issue if it comes to new job profiles. Many aspects were raised in the workshops. To have a comprehensive guideline for gender equality recommendation will be given:

- (a) Exchange with other partners of the DigiTeRRI project on their finding on gender equality or gender mainstreaming – what best practices are implemented; taking part in their initiatives
- (b) Analysis what special offers are found in the territory of Styria with respect to transition to digitalisation (initiatives, training, gender equality plan);
- (c) Showing the gap – what is needed, giving advice to companies and public authorities; (d) Deriving recommendations

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Government, Education research, industry and public joined the action, in particular females.

Number of participants: 50

Communication/PR activities: DigiTeRRI webpage, social media posts – twitter and linked in, personal invitations via mailings <https://digiterri.eu/digiterri-styria-female-talk/>, social media, and invitation of regional females in science, research and industry

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Knowledge & skills, Culture & values

Which gap will be closed with this action? Awareness for gender equality will help to prevent a gender equality gap in new digital professions.

Action result/-s: Active dialog on gender equality was started in the territory, highlighting the need of an action to reach gender equality that females can enter the labour market for digitalisation, the need for a females' network to exchange and support each other was raised, four-point list of recommendations to get more females involved in the field of digitalization.

Which effect do you anticipate? More initiatives in gender actions in the region and reaching RRI goals of gender equality

Responsible organisation/actor: Brigitte Kriszt, Montanuniversitaet

Planning and organisation of the action: Montanuniversitaet Leoben

3.2.3 Action #3 - Fit4MINT

Name (kind) of action: Discussion forum

Status: Ongoing

Date and location: January 2022, Physical or Digital Workshop Gymnasium Judenburg or Montanuniversitaet

Finish: December 2022

Description of the action: Educational goals in the STEM area should be clearly defined and communicated between the educational levels and institutions involved. Specifically, attention should be paid to the transition area between AHS and technical university. For this purpose, a networking conference with representatives from both areas should be organised. The university's expectations regarding the educational level of first- year students in the STEM area (specifically the subjects mathematics, physics, chemistry, computer science) are to be communicated and compared with the actual current conditions of the upper secondary school. The aim is to jointly identify possible measures to improve the transition between AHS and university.

State of the action implementation: Workshops with experts on didactics on programming and computer languages.

3.2.4 Action #4 - Exchange of Student Unions

Name (kind) of action: Discussion forum

Status: Completed

Date and location: October 2021, online/web

Finish: January 2022

Description of the action: To support the cross regional networking from the student's side, ideas on studies, student's cooperation using digital means and perspectives were shared among the students taking part in the project. This way, students can work on strategies on how to publish the results of the roadmap to the other students and how to arise interest for events.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Academia, students

Number of participants: 5

Communication/PR activities: Invitation to representative of student unions, participants nominated by the partners of the territories, invitation of student unions from outside the DigiTeRRI Territories.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Knowledge & skills, Networks & collaboration, Cross regional networking, higher education

Which gap will be closed with this action? Application of digital communication ways for exchange with other student unions, to derive new ways of networking, new exchange environment, usability of digital territorial networking, highlighting the students' needs for international lecturer exchange and digital teaching to bridge geographic distances, improving the teaching options, new studies and interaction in study.

Action result/-s: Increased knowledge on students' relation on Covid-19 studying and digital exchange, digital studying abroad, access to international research and opportunities of digitalization in teaching, new ideas for digital supported learning and digital lecturer exchange.

Which effect do you anticipate? Ideas for online options in international studying, RRI orientation in young scientist studies and science education.

Responsible organisation/actor: Christina Windisch-Kern, Brigitte Kriszt and Julia Brandstetter Montanuniversitaet

Planning and organisation of the action: Students' Unit Montanuniversitaet Leoben (Julia Brandstetter), Christina Windisch-Kern

3.2.5 Action #5 - DigitalLab

Name (kind) of action: Stakeholder integration, development of devices for the digital lab for teachers and students

Status: Ongoing

Date and location: December 2021, Physical Events, Leoben, Graz, Kapfenberg

Finish: September 2022

Description of the action: (1) Digital competences should be built up starting at kindergarten and primary school age. To support this, the following projects are to be initiated in the teaching- learning laboratory, which the Montanuniversitaet operates together with the Private University College of Teacher Education Augustinum (formerly KPH Graz): Development of at least one workshop on the topic of robotics/coding for the age group of 5 to 11-year-olds: (i) Cooperation with the HTL Kapfenberg, which is designing a mini-robot that can be programmed by children in a playful way as part of a school project and is bringing it to series production readiness. (ii) Development of workshop content by Montanuniversität Leoben and PPH Augustinum in cooperation with HTL Kapfenberg. (iii) Development of accompanying pedagogical material by PPH Augustinum Establishment of the workshops in the Teaching-Learning-Lab Leoben Embedding of the developed contents in teacher training and further education by the PPH Augustinum. (2) Extension of the existing workshops (topics “raw materials/salts”, “plastics”, “metals (incl. magnetism)”) by experiment stations with digital tools: Playful teaching of digital skills to pupils as well as to teachers in vocational training and education (cooperation with PPH Augustinum). Additional partners are to be brought on board for the projects, e.g., HTL Leoben and other educational institutions, companies. Dissemination is planned in cooperation with the Directorate of Education.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Education research, academia

Number of participants: 25 participants or engaged stakeholder

Communication/PR activities: Report on the webpage of DigiTeRRI is planned.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives:
Knowledge & skills

Which gap will be closed with this action? Teachers have to be trained; topic were included in curricular recently; Not sufficient general knowledge available, special knowledge has to be built up; Access to excellent hardware for supporting learning process not always available.

Action result/-s: RRI goals, science education of young people, closing the gap of schools and universities, opening science for pupils

Which effect do you anticipate? Make young children in the world of digitalisation more understandable, increase engagement in studies.

Responsible organisation/actor: Julia Mayerhofer -Lillie, Montanuniversitaet

Planning and organisation of the action: Montanuniversitaet Leoben

3.2.6 Action #6 - Awareness of the Styrian Roadmap

Name (kind) of action: Stakeholder integration and information about the roadmap

Status: Completed

Date and location: December 2021, physical, hybrid and digital initiatives

Finish: May 2022

Description of the action: Reaching awareness on the roadmap in the territory of Styria

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Academia, Government, Society, Education research, Education, public administration

Number of participants: At least 400 people were reached by sending the printed roadmap and taking part in the stakeholder core group information meeting

Communication/PR activities: Printing of roadmap, webpage, social media, personal invitations by mailings or letters

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Leadership, spreading the roadmap outcomes and needed initiatives in the territory, knowledge build up and capacity building on measures for transition – anticipation and co-creation

Which gap will be closed with this action? Gap of lack of knowledge on the roadmap outcomes, engaging more stakeholder in the implementation of the developed initiatives, roadmap is available in written form, helps to reach transparency

Action result/-s: Increased knowledge on the Styrian Roadmap after the project period documented and sustained knowledge representing the need of stakeholders.

Which effect do you anticipate? Increased awareness of the roadmap, need for transition taking into account of societal needs and RRI orientation

Responsible organisation/actor: Brigitte Kriszt, Montanuniversitaet

Planning and organisation of the action: Montanuniversitaet

3.2.7 Action #7 - Concept development "Styria Universal platform"

Name (kind) of action: Concept on a platform, study for development of a platform, dissemination of the outcomes

Status: Completed

Date and location: September 2021, Online and physical workshops, concept development

Finish: April 2022

Description of the action: The ultimate interface of all areas of life. It connects individual needs in terms of their social and cultural functions within society. It supports and guides through all areas of life from childcare to across all educational paths. Regional entrepreneurs find employees to match them or motivate people to train in specific niches before bottlenecks arise. A platform that respects ethical aspects of our society in the region and provides us with the information we need via depersonalized data in real time. It warns us of floods or avalanches and helps us to fulfil our duties as citizens and guides us through official regulations. A trusted platform for the whole region. The following aspects are considered separately: Technological possibilities, Ethical aspects.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Academia, Government, Society, Education research, Education

Number of participants: 55

Communication/PR activities: Introduced at the training on social media.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Networks & collaboration, Communication.

Which gap will be closed with this action? The gap of extensive possibility for interaction, no common platform visible.

Action result/-s: Key point for development of a Styria Universal platform

Which effect do you anticipate? Increased awareness on the available platform solutions.

Responsible organisation/actor: Franz Edler, Zentrum für angewandte Technologie Leoben and Julia Schmidbauer, Montanuniversitaet Leoben.

Planning and organisation of the action: Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Zentrum für angewandte Technologie Leoben

3.2.8 Action #8 – Training on digital marketing in social media

Name (kind) of action: Training online

Status: Completed

Date and location: January 2022, Physical/Web-Stream

Finish: April 2022

Description of the action: Seminar with stakeholders from the Upper Styria region who are reluctant to digitize, despite all the signs on the market. How long can someone stay in such a market segment or will hybrid market strategies prevail. What are the dangers and opportunities of hybrid or purely web-based sales platforms? What scenarios are emerging on the digital market in the next 5 to 10 years. Trading at the bottom of reality in a digital world.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: industry, business, public administration

Number of participants: 49

Communication/PR activities: Invitation to the stakeholder representatives of Styria, Start ups

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Leadership, business & market

Which gap will be closed with this action? Market, structural barriers, getting awareness, attracting stakeholder from abroad, digital territorial exchange and cooperation.

Action result/-s: Best practices sharing from platform provider and municipalities Leoben, Bruck/MUR and Linz. Future Development from the view of the universities. Knowledge dissemination on digital marketing in social media, tools and digital marketing for digitalisation officer of municipalities and companies.

Which effect do you anticipate? Higher capacities of start-ups in the digital global market, societal engagement, digitalisation of municipalities, presentation in platforms and social media

Responsible organisation/actor: Franz Edler, Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Zentrum für angewandte Technologie Leoben

Planning and organisation of the action: Zentrum für angewandte Technologie Leoben

3.2.9 Action #9 - Incubator exchange for fostering entrepreneurship in digitalisation

Name (kind) of action: Discussion forum

Status: Completed

Date and location: January 2022, online /web

Finish: July 2022

Description of the action: Develop digital awareness programs and encourage potential founders of their own start-up in a digital environment. Network interface between entrepreneurs with compatible interests and promote or support international market expansion efforts. Promoting digital processes in business management and technical cooperation between companies or expanding digital opportunities to ensure the economic strength of the regions. The cross regional Incubator network supports the development of the digital transformation of the regions through their collaboration and elaboration of risks & opportunities for young companies regarding sustainable growth strategies.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Academia

Number of participants: 85

Communication/PR activities: Mailing, webpage, social media, personal talks

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Networks & collaboration, Leadership, business & market

Which gap will be closed with this action? The gap of extensive possibility for interaction of incubators

Action result/-s: Build-up knowledge for a digital world, reaching of research and innovation by digital presentation, skills in designing digital boost, feedback from experts on design and presentation, dissemination of start-up in digitalization

Which effect do you anticipate? Network and cooperation of incubator, better knowledge of start-up in digital presentation of their companies, professional boost design for digital fairs

Responsible organisation/actor: Franz Edler, Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Zentrum für angewandte Technologie Leoben

Planning and organisation of the action: Zentrum für angewandte Technologie Leoben

3.2.10 Action #10 – Cross Regional Event – B2B Networking event on industry and digitalisation

Name (kind) of action: Exchange and meeting event

Status: Completed

Date and location: January 2022, Online /web

Digital Cooperation Day 2022 powered by DigiTeRRI, 31.5.2022

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: Stakeholders from Styria Grand Est and Värmland and other European territories were invited for a one-day online event. Before the event the participants can give information about them and their interests on the event-homepage. Lectures guide the event. In Styria we would have available lectures about: digital transformation of small businesses, support through digitalisation for businesses. The program will include the introduction of the DigiTeRRI project, the territories, some companies partner and the research organisations. For the digital event a registration platform will be set up, in which participating organisations can give their profile in advance and the individual exchange meetings on digitalisation can be performed. The European Enterprise network will also be engaged.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Academia, Government, Education research, Education from the DigiTeRRI territories and other EUROPEAN regions and third countries

Number of participants: 50

Communication/PR activities: B2match platform, mailing, webpage, social media.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Technology, Networks & collaboration, Leadership, business & market, Communication

Which gap will be closed with this action? Cross regional learning and exchange, attracting other companies and partner for cooperation with the Styrian region in the field of application of digital solutions, offering new cooperation option to local companies, exchange on regional development options

Action result/-s: Network formation, business opportunities, research collaboration, and exchange in digital teaching, innovation options

Which effect do you anticipate? New opportunities of online cooperation and innovation potential, fostering the cross territorial exchange and cooperation

Responsible organisation/actor: Brigitte Kriszt and Renate Reumueller, Montanuniversitaet

Planning and organisation of the action: Montanuniversitaet Leoben supported by representatives from Värmland and Grand Est.

3.2.11 Action #11 – Plan Scan & Shop – explore the regional economy and important facilities online

Name (kind) of action: Implementation of a digital link of physical shops of Bruck/Mur and digital shopping options

Status: Completed

Date and location: January 2022, physical link at shops, central facilities, etc. to an online platform – feature of the universal online platform, concept development

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: With graphically uniformly designed notices, which contain a QR code, on business areas, important facilities, etc., a link is made with underlying platforms, online shops, etc. This enables interested parties to obtain information, shop online, etc. at a low-threshold and outside of opening hours. Example: the city of Bruck an der Mur offers its businesses under “www.wirtschaft-bruckmur.at” a uniform platform with individual web presentations by the participating businesses. The ability to access information about the company or its online shop quickly and easily using a QR code at the store is intended to further increase its attractiveness.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Society

Number of participants: 120 shops

Communication/PR activities: Bruck internal action, personal contact.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Leadership, business & market

Which gap will be closed with this action? Low-threshold access to the topic of e-commerce and the associated expansion of these activities - also on the part of the company, if this enables new additional target groups to be tapped.

Action result/-s: Increasing the number of hits on websites and online shops or motivating customers to deal more intensively with the technology and the company by scanning the QR code.

Which effect do you anticipate? Increased digital availability for shops in Bruck an der Mur.

Responsible organisation/actor: Eric Weber, Standort Marketing Bruck an der Mur

Planning and organisation of the action: Standort und Marketing Bruck an der Mur

3.2.12 Action #12 - Job platform for municipality co-workers

Name (kind) of action: Concept for building a platform for employees' exchange of regional municipalities

Status: Completed

Date and location: October 2021, Online / Web, discussion round, studies, concept development

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: Many communities are increasingly confronted with the problem of meeting their staffing needs - at all levels of education. In the past, the municipalities were in demand as employers because they offered secure long-term employment, but this picture has now changed. At the moment, the economy lures with significantly higher wages than the collective agreements of the municipalities allow. In addition, the attitude of the working population to the issue of "stability" has changed. A more frequent job change is valued differently now than it was a few years ago. New ways must therefore be found as to how municipalities can acquire their staff in the future and which measures can / must be taken in order to make these jobs more attractive. Ideas for these are: Common job platforms of municipalities Personal pools; Cross-community employment (e.g., lifeguard in summer and ice master in winter; at different communities), digital working environment.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Government, Society, public administration

Number of participants: 4

Communication/PR activities: Mailing, personal invitations.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Networks & collaboration, Communication.

Which gap will be closed with this action? Creation of new access to the labour market, better access to employees are components in the public administration of municipalities.

Action result/-s: Knowledge on the initial situation need and challenges as well as ideas and suggestions for a Job platform for municipality co-workers.

Which effect do you anticipate? A developed Job platform for municipality co-workers.

Responsible organisation/actor: Eric Weber, Standort Marketing Bruck an der Mur

Planning and organisation of the action: Standort und Marketing Bruck an der Mur

3.3 Implementation Process - Grand Est

The management of the implementation process of the chosen actions in Grand Est Region was taken care of by the three partners in the project, Grand E-Nov+, Materialia, Université de Lorraine and the DigiTeRRI external actors as Grand Est Region, Communicasciences, Plastinnov, who's participated to the DigiTeRRI sessions and roadmap workshops. The assigned action managers for each action belonged to these organizations.

Several meetings were held by video conference according to the need to exchange on the actions and 3 physical meetings have allowed the three actors, Grand Est partners, to meet and work on actions process since the summer of 2021.

The coordination to keep track on the implementation process belongs to Grand E-Nov. Grand E-Nov was responsible for the planning and the execution of the actions related to regional strategy for digital aspects- transition (action #1-5), Materialia for these actions aiming at the business/industry sector (#6, 8, 10). Université de Lorraine took over the responsibility for the academia/government/industry sector (#7, 9-12). Action 11 was managed by Communicasciences structure.

In the implementation of the first 9 actions, the majority of the actions has been respected in terms of content and deadlines.

For a couple of the actions there are some deviations. Action #3 "Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) of Region Grand Est (2021-2027)", we organized two workshops with the Region focused on the integration of KPIs issued from RRI in the S3 for the period 2020-2027. The S3 is still under discussion between the Region Grand Est and the DG REGION, so we do not formally integrate KPIs in the S3. We have yet to identify KPIs for the follow-up of funded projects (ethical dimension for digital projects, % of women entrepreneurs,) and the action will be finalized before the end of 2022.

Action 7: Company and academic mutualized training: increasing digital skills through innovative educational workshops", the partner UL from Grand Est has carried out as planned the action. The common activities between Värmland and Grand Est have been postponed from March to September 2022. The deviation is explained due to the lack of participants from Värmland that needs to revamp the program of activities.

Action 11 Special event during Est'ival des Sciences Event has been included in the first 9 actions. The event took place on 25 June 2022 and not in July 2022.

Actions within the project but outside the timeframe for this report are:

Action #3 Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of Region Grand Est (2021-2027), Action #10 RRI awareness-raising video, and Action #12 Survey on RRI practices in the FabLabs of the Grand Est Region. These actions will still be implemented, however, after the DigiTeRRI project end.

Name	M21 Sep 21	M22 Oct 21	M23 Nov 21	M24 Dec 21	M25 Jan 22	M26 Feb 22	M27 Mar 22	M28 Apr 22	M29 May 22	M30 Jun 22*	M31 Jul 22	M32 Aug 22	M33 Sep 22	M34 Oct 22	M35 Nov 22	M36 Dec 22
Integration of RRI concept in the future European Digital Innovation Hub																
Encourage young girls to digital sector																
Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of Region Grand Est (2021-2027)																
RRI criteria for public funding																
AI ethical Manifesto																
Sharing best practices on information search tools																
Company and academic mutualized training: increasing digital skills through innovative educational workshops																
UTTOPIA - innovation challenge																
CE IAMOT Conference: scientific/industrial/institutional meetings																
RRI awareness - raising video																
Estival des Sciences Event																
Survey on RRI practices in the FabLabs of the Grand Est Region																

M21-M32: 9 implemented actions

M33-M36: Additional 3 implemented actions

*Due date implementation report

Figure 6: Time implementation of actions in Grand Est

3.3.1 Action #1 – Integration of RRI concept in the future European Digital Innovation Hub

Name (kind) of action: Training

Status: Completed

Date and location: December 2021, Grand Est

Finish: May 2022

Description of the action: The European Commission will launch the Digital Europe Program end Q3/2022. A part of the call will be focused on the setting up of a European network Digital Innovation Hub per European region. The objective is to accelerate advanced digitalisation of industrial SMEs thanks to integration of technologies and services based on Artificial intelligence, cyber-security and High Performance Computing (HPC) . The main topics: test before investment, training, funding and networking. The action will be focused on the integration of RRI topics as ethics and Inclusion in the activities of EDIH.

Ethics is covered through : setting up of an ethical committee to manage issues related to integration of technologies and services based on artificial intelligence. We will identify different training courses and schools that propose “non-traditional training” (second chance schools,) and they will be integrated in the future catalogue of training of the EDIH. Activities linked to the setting up of a virtual regional Digital Institute.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Society, Education research, Education

Number of participants: 15 – Grand E-nov+ and the main partners of the initiative.

Communication/PR activities: Call for expression of interest to identify companies that will join EDIH activities. Panel discussion with others EDIH candidates and the European Commission (360 Grand Est – Strasbourg 7th December 2021) – Panel discussion with other French EDIH Initiatives (VIVATECH – Paris – 17th of June 2022).

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Knowledge & skills, “Enable all talents in the Grand Est to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector”

Which gap will be closed with this action? Increase the number of people trained with digital skills, competencies in the digital, increase digitalisation of SMEs by integration of specific skills, increase the number of people trained that could work in companies

Action result/-s: Project submitted to the EC the 22nd of February 2022.

Which effect do you anticipate? Acquire digital skills via a tailored training. Integration of RRI concepts in the services provided to the SME's

Responsible organisation/actor: Jean-Jacques Bernardini, Grand E-nov +

Planning and organisation of the action: 7th December 2021: launch of action "360 Grand Est event" | December – February 2022: integration of RRI Elements in the proposal submitted to the EC (22th February) | February-May 2022: follow up

3.3.2 Action #2 - Encourage young girls to digital sector

Name (kind) of action: Discussion forum

Status: Completed

Date and location: October 2021, Online + Physical event (hybrid)

Finish: December 2021

Description of the action: This is a raising awareness campaign which targeted young girls in secondary schools on the subject of technological and scientific training and professional careers in the digital and industrial sectors through mentoring by women leaders, experts and professionals in the digital field. In order to effectively raise awareness of the importance of RRI and gender equality, the DigiTeRRI Grand Est team delivered a series of presentations, during a series of events.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Academia, Society, Education

Number of participants: -Event Robotech Girls: 902 participants for all virtual events. No information on participant concerning Grand E-Nov stand when we promoted DigiTeRRI

-Event Smart City Week: More than 350 participants integrating: more than 300 young girls at high school levels, 8 high schools of three employment bassins, 8 companies: Batigère, Vinci construction, Dalkia, PC Circulation Métropole du Grand Nancy, Eiffage, SPIE and RTE, 7 engineering schools, 20 executives women having digital jobs.

-Support: 4 engineers schools from Grand Est: More precisely, three main events have been organized with regional association: two with Elles Bougent. These events took place in engineering schools and during a professional trade show about digitalization. Presentations were held about digital jobs description, RRI and testimonies.

- Robotech girls journey at event BE4.0 Mulhouse (Awareness-raising event for young high school girls during the Be Est trade fair (industry of the future) 21 high school girls from 3 different classes from one high school from Mulhouse city.

Communication/PR activities: Social media, DigiTeRRI website, PR

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives:

Knowledge and skills, Enable all talents in the Grand Est to seize opportunities offered by the digital sector

Which gap will be closed with this action? Increase the number of applications from young girls for digital-related training and jobs (including in higher education). It is worth noting that more than 350 young female high school students will participate in these actions. One other main gap is the negative representation of young females against digital jobs, then few of them applied to digital higher education programs.

Action result/-s: One major result is a change in the young women mindset about digital activities and jobs. Breaking the barriers considering representations about female professional opportunities. Note that most of the participants have to choose their educational orientation in March. So, the challenge was to give them all materials to open their wishes about education. The number of participants was very good, so that this action will be organized each year in the future. The main observable result is the very high involvement of high schools' managers and professors, company executives, engineering schools' professors and students. Another outcome is relating to the demand of companies to enlarge the action to the college level.

A quiz developed and presented at the BE 4.0 trade fair to secondary school girls in paper format was developed as an application thanks to our partner in the WeDo project. This application is currently being developed and may even be developed in different languages and adapted according to the specificities of the partner territories.

Which effect do you anticipate? Enable all talents in the Grand Est to seize opportunities offered by the digital sector "Increased interest among young girls to apply technical programmes at the university

Responsible organisation/actor: Grand E-Nov+, ENSGSI-Université de Lorraine, CCI Alsace Eurometropole, Elles Bougent association

Planning and organisation of the action:

October 2021: First action Preparations

14-15th October 2021: action Robotech Girls Online (virtual event)

14th October 2021: Smart City Week, physical event

1rd December: Be Est 4.0 Event (physical event)

3.3.3 Action #3 - Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of Region Grand Est (2021-2027)

Name (kind) of action: Workshop

Status: Ongoing

Date and location: Starting date October 2021, Grand Est, Physical meeting could be possible

Finish: December 2022

Description of the action: The European Commission asked to the Regions to define a Smart Specialisation Strategy that will be annexed to the operational plan (OP) 2021-2027 for ERDF use. Region Grand Est has defined 8 market priorities and 4 transversal priorities. One of those transversal priorities is entitled “responsible innovation”. The objective of the action is to use RRI criteria to - Integrate them in the selection criteria of projects that will be funded. - Integrate them in the follow-up and the evaluation of the performance of the projects funded by the ERDF.

3.3.4 Action #4 - RRI criteria for public funding

Name (kind) of action: Implementation action

Status: Completed

Date and location: April 2020, No specific location

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: Grand Est region has a strong willingness to help companies in their digital transformation and to launch disruptive projects. Companies (SME, Startups) could solicit different regional fundings for their development. Specially in artificial intelligence (AI) field, the AI plan offers different fundings, the Bonus AI (50k€) for startups, the Primo AI (50k€) and DIAG AI (5k€) for SME.

Companies have to fill a template for their demands. Grand E-Nov+ is mobilized for reviewing the demand and advice Grand Est region is the acceptance of financing. For this reviewing we use RRI references as criteria for social impact, ethics, and environmental liability. Instances of RRI questions in our template:

- Bonus AI: Describe the consideration of the impact of your solution on people (in terms of employment, quality of life at work, individual freedoms, exercise of democracy, etc.).
- DIAG AI: Have you implemented tools to explain the results of the algorithm (ethics, transparency of results, open data, ...)?

Further to this reviewing, we organized different events to promote these fundings and communicate to the RRI criterias.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Government

Number of participants: Here, all the companies which solicited a Bonus AI, Primo AI and DIAG AI funding:

BONUS AI: companies	BONUS AI: people	PRIMO AI: companies	PRIMO AI: people
Urban loop	Jean-Phillipe Mangeot	Nicolas Feuillatte	François GREGOIRE
DCMCC France	CYRIL.DERONNE	INTERLINK SAS	
RDS DIAG	Melissa Guyot	COMMERCIA	Rose André
ATIXYS	Arnaud Tonon	SAMM TRADING	Antony VILLEGER
XTRAMILE	Sarah CHRAVAUX	Petit Bateau	Sophie Escario
APREX Solution	Sarah CHRAVAUX	Niandhji	
SYSARK	Sarah CHRAVAUX	AccessREC	Yannick Ragon
NABU	Sarah CHRAVAUX	INERA GE	BAUDIN Christophe
Elixir Health	Mathieu	HAPPISO	SAS HAPPISO

BONUS AI: companies	BONUS AI: people	PRIMO AI: companies	PRIMO AI: people
VASA	Jean-Sébastien Lefèvre	THEPLACETOWISH	Sylvie
INDOOR Santé	Johan Pascal	4iTEC	
Anamnote	Charles-Antoine Robert	Groupe Altaïr	Claire PIERRON
HRBS	hrbs@orange.fr	ENERBIOFLEX	Julien DELGOVE
Thoth	Jonas Petit		
Komportementalist	Frédérique Gutlé		
IMKI TECH	Frédéric ROSE		
SOUNDUCT	Olivier Gauthier		
CEPHALGO	lisa.chiang@cephalgo.com		
OPTIIVE	eric.halter@optiive.com		

DIAG AI:

ORGANISME			
Nom	Site web	Prénom	Nom
Artelys	www.artelys.com	Paul-Alexandre	Bouhana
Bial-X	www.bial-x.com	Jacques-Henri	Brousse
Captronic	www.captronic.fr	Jean-Christophe	Marpeau
CQTNC	www.cqtnc.fr	Olivier	Perrin
Cross Data	www.crossdata.tech	Jean-Charles	Rongère
DataScope	www.datascope.fr	Ekaterina	Yushina
Himydata	www.himydata.com	David	Bessoudo
IBM Interactive	www.ibminteractive.fr	Matthieu	Henry d'Aulnois
JustAI	www.justai.com	Louise	Magat
Neomia	www.neomia.ai	Yannick	Boehmann
Niji	www.niji.fr/diagnostic-ia-data	Clément	Rouquié
Numalis	www.numalis.com	Arnault	loulalalen

<https://www.grandest.fr/vos-aides-regionales/diagnostic-ia/>

Communication/PR activities: Web page for the fundings "Primo IA" : <https://www.grandest.fr/vos-aides-regionales/aide-aux-entreprises-primo-utilisatrices-dintelligence-artificielle/>

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives:
Technology, Increasing social responsibility as part of a digital transformation process

Which gap will be closed with this action? With RRI criteria in the process of funding assignment, we are sure public funding will impact positively our society with responsible innovative projects

Action result/-s: More than one million euros are engaged in project of companies which embed different RRI dimensions thank to the focus the region has on RRI criteria for their fundings.

Which effect do you anticipate? Develop and implement policies and related strategies to foster responsible digitalisation

Responsible organisation/actor: Alexis Steiner, Grand E-nov +

Planning and organisation of the action:

Q2 2020 : design of funding template

Q3 2020 : start of experimental phases

Q3 2021 : New regional strategy launched "Business Act II"

2022 : deployment

3.3.5 Action #5 - AI ethical Manifesto

Name (kind) of action: Demonstration event

Status: Completed

Date and location: July 2021, Physical and web (hybrid version)

Finish: December 2022

Description of the action: Artificial intelligence is increasingly impacting businesses and people's lives. This new technology raises questions about trust, transparency, and ethics. This is why designers of artificial intelligence must take into account the impact on humans in their development. Hence the importance of drafting a reference document that provides a framework and best practices for ethical artificial intelligence.

The aim of this action is to write and spread a guideline for sharing best practices to develop artificial intelligence algorithms. Our target are mainly students in computer sciences school and also algorithms designers.

1) Step one: Production of a document – Guideline for an ethical approach in support of the development artificial intelligence algorithms (<http://ai-ethical.com/131-2/>). We gathered many people from different companies to share their experiences and their needs to develop responsible algorithms. Thanks to these materials, we wrote a manifesto and a guideline.

2) Step two: Disseminating communication elements and promotion of the manifesto in company and school meetings. Highlight during the event 360 Grand Est and the signature of Grand Est President Region.

3) Step three: Participation in the launch event of the AI Ethical Manifesto and submission to the Secretary of State for the Digital Economy of the French Republic (this last step was delayed for France President election)

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Government

Number of participants: 10. All the writers:

Laurence DEVELLERS,
Professeure en IA à
l'Institut Data IA

Charles BOUYEYRON,
Directeur de l'Institut 3IA
Côte d'Azur

Roxana RUGINA,
Secrétaire Générale
d'Impact AI

Sophie VIGER, Directrice
Générale de l'école 42

Tawhid CHTIOUI,
Président-fondateur &
Dean d'avancity

Magali BARNQIN,
Animatrice du numérique,
Data & IA de Telecom
Valley

Antoine TROTET, Chef
du service Révolution
Numérique de la
région Grand Est

Gaëlle PINSON,
Directrice Générale du
Hub France IA

Nicolas VIALLET,
Directeur Opérationnel
ANITI, Université de
Toulouse

Alexis STEINER, Chef
de projets IA et Numérique
de Grand E-Nov+

Additionally to the signature of the Grand Est President of the Manifesto, we organised a roundtable discussion during the event in December 2021: 360 Grand Est (replay here: <https://www.360grandest.fr/fr/session/4f52b9a0-7532-ec11-ae72-a04a5e7d345e>)

We invited mister Gégout to share his experience to implement the guideline of AI Manifesto.

Communication/PR activities: 360 Grand Est website, social media

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Technology, Creating the conditions for the development of "responsible" digital products and services

Which gap will be closed with this action? AI solutions developed with RRI-by-design concept, thanks to manifesto AI ethical will have a positive impact on the users and society

Action result/-s: The region council has signed the manifesto to promote this initiative during the event 360 Grand Est. More than 2000 companies were attendees during this event and could see the commitment of the Grand Est region to promote responsible artificial intelligence.

Which effect do you anticipate? Sharing good practices

Responsible organisation/actor: Alexis Steiner, Grand E-nov +

Planning and organisation of the action: Q1 Q2 2021: drafting the charter

Q3 2021: launch of the charter

Q4 2021 / Q1 2022: promotion of the charter

3.3.6 Action #6 - Sharing best practices on information search tools

Name (kind) of action: Competence

Status: Completed

Date and location: January 2022, Online

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: SMEs, civil society, universities, and research institutions, among other, need to embrace digitalisation and use technological tools. Nevertheless, the tools and methodologies to look for the right information are sometimes unknown. Plus, COVID-19 and fake news have revealed the importance of anticipation and the gathering of good strategic information. The objective is that information search tools are known by the Q-helix stakeholders, so that they can adapt digitalisation

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Society, Education research, Education

Number of participants: 27. SMEs, associations and clusters, students, consultants, and other stakeholders

Communication/PR activities: Filter the target audience, dissemination of the event (newsletter, social media), send the invitations with the Zoom/Teams link, provide participants with feedback and the replay video

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Knowledge and skills, Giving as many people as possible the opportunity to discover digital technologies

Which gap will be closed with this action? Stakeholders such as SMEs, universities, research institutions and also civil society learned best practices on information search, providing them with the anticipation and the resilience needed to face new unexpected crisis and embrace digitalisation.

Action result/-s: As a result of this action, a group of stakeholders in the Grand Est Region are now aware of the importance of information monitoring tools to guarantee the competitiveness of SMEs and entrepreneurs.

-Stakeholders such as SMEs and entrepreneurs will be more prepared to face future crisis

-SMEs will get to know information monitoring tools

-SMEs worried about information monitoring will know each other and share good practices

Which effect do you anticipate? Sharing good practices

Responsible organisation/actor: Lucia Gonzalez; Materialia

Planning and organisation of the action: Q1: preparation Q2: event

3.3.7 Action #7 - Company and academic mutualized training: increasing digital skills through innovative educational workshops

Name (kind) of action: Training

Status: Completed

Date and location: October 2021, Nancy France

Finish: May 2022

Description of the action: Agile workshop ("72 heures agiles"):

Training is organized for company executives simultaneously with students. They all get the same lectures and work together on a specific digital problem of the companies involved. The main topic relates to agile methodologies applied to digital projects. The methodologies are presented through short lectures and, alternatively, participants work in groups applying these methodologies on problems proposed by the companies. New digital applications or web sites prototypes are developed, and the concepts are argued during a final defence. All along the design process, participants are questioned about the potential RRI impact of their solution. At the end of the module, they fill in a questionnaire assessing this RRI dimension.

Digital Summer School is a complementary to the "72 heures agiles, agile workshop" module. A three day Summer School has been organized in May 2022, with the same pedagogical content. This Summer School targeted PhD students: 38 from Université de Lorraine (France-Grand Est) and 24 from Kaiserslautern University (Germany). They all worked on the same digital problem trying to find responsible solutions. The industrial network "Technologie-Initiative SmartFactoryKL e.V was associated to this action.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Society, Education research, Education

Number of participants: 40 participants: students and executives in France.

Communication/PR activities: some articles have been disseminated through Twitter and Facebook

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Networks & collaboration: Objects, goal: Creating the conditions for the development of "responsible" digital products and services

Which gap will be closed with this action? Diffusion of RRI concepts -increase of the skills of company executives and managers in the field of Agility, - increase of students' skills, - common experience between students and experienced people, - an innovative educational process, Digital summer school: Impacts are the same. A focus has also been made on ethic in research

Action result/-s: The participants received a training course about agile methodologies and also worked on a short project given by companies. They produce a mock-up. They acquired skills adapted to digital project. Moreover, contacts between students and executives help the youngest to get a supplementary experience about professional postures. Finally, the RRI concepts have been learned by participants through a series of evaluation steps during the module: the questions were about the RRI impact of the technical propositions.

Which effect do you anticipate? This module has been presented to DigiTeRRI members. As it is corresponding to academic and industrial needs in each of the three territories, a transfer from Grand Est to the other regions has been decided. From February to May 2022 weekly meetings between Karlstad University and Université de Lorraine were held to transfer the module management know-how to Värmland academics and to re-design the documents used during the training. The module will be organized in September in Karlstad.

Responsible organisation/actor: Vincent Boly and Davy Monticolo, Université de Lorraine

Planning and organisation of the action: preparation of the module one in France: January 22 + organization of the module in France from 15th to 18th of February + identification and invitation of future participants + preparation of the second module in Värmland: from February to May 2022 April 2022 + organization of the second module: last week September 2022 of May

3.3.8 Action #8 - UTTOPIA (technology transfer and technical orientation unit for prototyping and artificial intelligence) - innovation challenge

Name (kind) of action: Stakeholder integration

Status: Completed

Date and location: December 2021, Forbach, Grand Est region. Possibility of doing it online.

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: Plastinnov is launching UTTOPIA, a technology transfer and technical orientation unit for prototyping and artificial intelligence. In the Forbach territory, an innovative third place will be built, creating synergies between different stakeholders such as the local incubator Eurodev Center – Interface, high schools, and a university. As part of the launch of UTTOPIA, an innovation challenge will be launched, providing project holders support and technical follow-up by Plastinnov Associate professors (technical profiles keen on factory 4.0 digitalisation) and Materialia. RRI criteria will be taken into account.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ffradet_formation-recherche-pme-activity-6900884297675599872-vMX0

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Society

Number of participants: 20-30

Communication/PR activities: Kick off of UTTOPIA on December 2021

-April 2022: Innovation Challenges

-Visit to UTTOPIA by the DigiTeRRI team on June 2022

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives:

Technology, Knowledge and skills, Networks & collaboration, Enable all talents in the Grand Est to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector

Which gap will be closed with this action? Thanks to the innovation challenge, as part of the UTTOPIA initiative, civil society such as unemployed or refugees will embrace digitalisation and learn from new methods and technologies

Action result/-s: -Inclusion, as civil society will get to better know digitalisation and additive manufacturing

-Vulgarisation of science

Which effect do you anticipate? Supporting citizens in the development of digital projects

Responsible organisation/actor: Lucia Gonzalez; Materialia

Planning and organisation of the action: UTTOPIA was launched in December 2021 in front of an audience composed of elected officials from the region, industrialists, and students. This launch was an opportunity to present the platform and its technologies and to promote them to the public concerned.

In April 2022 an innovation challenge was organised. 17 students met in teams of 2 or 3 with the objective of learning through creation. For 3 days the teams were given a mechatronic project to design and build under the supervision and support of Plastinnov.

In June 2022, a visit was organised for local representatives of DIGITERRI. The objective was to present all the technologies present on UTTOPIA as well as the objectives of the platform.

3.3.9 Action #9 – (E IAMoT Conference: scientific/industrial/institutional meetings

Name (kind) of action: Presentation and discussion workshops about RRI

Status: Completed

Date and location: Event : 20/23 of June 2022, Palais des congrès de Nancy-France

Finish: June 2022

Description of the action: This event brought together researchers, companies, and institutions debating several different themes such as digitalization, innovation in local authorities and RRI. Papers from researchers were also scheduled, following a call for papers. This action also played a major role in terms of communication because many media were mobilized. Moreover, the best papers will be published in international journals.

The first one gathered five managers of European projects in the field of digitalization. After summaries of these projects, debates were held. One discussion concerned the place of the concept of responsibility in all these projects. A second workshop gathered authors of scientific papers about RRI. This paper session helped improving the concept of RRI and have a better understanding of its connection with transitions (mainly the digital transition). Finally, a third workshop was dedicated to DigiTeRRI, where members of the projects confront their outcomes to researchers, industries, and economic institutions at an international level.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Industry, Business, Society, Education research

Number of participants: About 300 people, attend the three workshops in total (face to face or online)

Communication/PR activities: a call for papers has been sent to research communities. A web site has been launched <https://ice-iamot-2022-conference.org/>. Moreover, Facebook and twitter are used to communicate. An editor will publish some papers. Mailing list are used to invite participants (companies, researchers, association managers and public executives)

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Networks & collaboration, Communication, “Enable all talents in the Grand Est to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector”

Which gap will be closed with this action? Impact: introduce and deepen the concepts of RRI and their impact on the life of citizens and the economy, share some experiences.

Action result/-s: Three workshops where held and debates have been recorded (available in line on the ICE-IAMOT congress website,

- Increased awareness of researchers and companies about RRI,
- Best papers published in an international journal special issue,
- Diffusion of the practical action manage by DigiTeRRI members in their territories.

Which effect do you anticipate? Acculturating to science

Responsible organisation/actor: Vincent Boly, Université de Lorraine

Planning and organisation of the action: Congress will be held from June the 19th to the 22th. January / Marsh: logistic preparation, call for papers and workshops organization. Marsh to June: fund raising, contacts with speakers

3.3.10 Action #10 - RRI awareness-raising video

Name (kind) of action: Implementation action

Status: Not started yet

Date and location: Not started

Finish: November 2022

Description of the action: In order to raise awareness of the importance of RRI to a wide range of stakeholders of the Quadruple Helix, a video/ series of videos will be developed. The objective is demonstrating different stakeholders the added value represented by RRI and how they can embrace it

3.3.11 Action #11 - RRI awareness-raising video

Name (kind) of action: Stakeholder integration

Status: Completed

Date and location: October 2021, Physical, Marbache, Grand Est Region

Finish: 25 June 2022

Description of the action: The EST'ival des Sciences consists of a tour of 10 scientific culture events in rural areas (villages from 700 to 2000 inhabitants), with one event per department in Grand Est the region. One of the main objectives is to bring science to the general public in "cultural deserts". The main target groups are teenagers (14+) and adults, regardless of their level of education. Scientists from public research laboratories in the region, and start-ups managers whose technology also comes from public research laboratories in the Grand Est, guided by a scientific mediator to help create a friendly atmosphere and make the content accessible to all. These are not conferences,

the format is interactive, fun, and based on exchanges between the participants and the scientists. The Events last around 2 hours and 15 minutes: 15 minutes for the reception of the public, between 1 hour and 1 hour and 30 minutes for the quiz format, 15 to 45 minutes for free discussion with the scientist(s). It was agreed that 2 of the 10 EST'ival des Sciences events would be devoted to digital science themes (in conjunction with Inria or the CNRS). The call for proposals to identify scientific speakers (lecturers, research fellows, doctoral students, etc.) was on 25 October 2021. It combined these "theoretical" presentations with the organisation of practical workshops in order to present technologies such as 3D printers, augmented reality, etc. in a concrete manner.

Target group(s) within quadruple helix: Society, Education research, Education

Number of participants: 18 participants (Age distribution: 26% - 18 // 7% 18 - 35 // 53% 36 - 65 // 14% + 65)

Communication/PR activities: Call for proposals to identify scientific speakers (lecturers, research fellows, doctoral students, etc.) was launched on 25 October 2021.

Use of web site: <https://www.centre-est.cnrs.fr/fr/evenement/estival-des-sciences-edition-2021>; <https://www.echosciences-grandest.fr/dossiers/est-ival-des-sciences-2021>. Information has been spread thanks to the city council, newspapers, but also using social communication tools as Twitter & Facebook and Echosciences Grand Est which is a server platform dedicated to map scientific events <https://www.echosciences-grandest.fr/evenements/l-impression-3d-une-histoire-d-empilement-1>.

Roadmap domain, overarching goal, and corresponding objectives: Knowledge and skills, Communication, Technology, Giving as many people as possible the opportunity to discover digital technologies

Which gap will be closed with this action? A scientific culture that is more widely distributed over the territory: aiming to reduce inequalities in access to scientific culture between urban and rural areas. Giving the opportunity to interact with researchers to participate in the creation of a science-society link.

Action result/-s: participants were against participating in this type of event again, on the contrary, they asked for more of them. Arouse the curiosity of inhabitants far from the major university centres for research work: no
Exchange about the importance of RRI objectives: participants agreed with the importance of the latter.

Which effect do you anticipate? Science acculturation

Responsible organisation/actor: Vincent Boly, Université de Lorraine -

Stéphanie Toussaint Grand E-Nov+ Anne Vincente, manager and partner's action: Consultant in Science and Innovation Mediation

Planning and organisation of the action: October to December 2021: Start of the construction of the pre-programme and partnerships, writing and submission of grant applications. January to June 2022: construction of the content of the events, construction of the communication plan and its execution.

Anne Vincente, partner's action: Consultant in Science and Innovation Mediation

3.3.12 Action #12 - Survey on RRI practices in the FabLabs of the Grand Est Region

Name (kind) of action: Study

Status: Ongoing

Date and location: February 2021, Grand Est region

Finish: September 2022

Description of the action: The aim is to raise awareness and identify RRI practices within the users of third places in the Grand Est region. A particular third place is chosen: the Lorraine Fab Living Lab. Indeed, the structure is used by companies, public collectivises, students and citizen association. So that a wide range of public may be studied during a long period (6 months). Different anthropological approaches are mobilized to understand the RRI perception of this third-place users: enquiry, in situ observation, workshop and games.

Appendix

January 2022

The implementation of the actions (based on the action plan D4.3) has been monitored. The monthly overview of the status of this monitoring is presented here. It started in January 2022 and lasted till June 2022. Each monthly overview starts with a snap-shot of all three territories together. Next, the information on each territory is presented, starting with Grand Est, followed by Styria and Värmland.

D5.1 – Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/12/21 Starting date
30/09/22 Ending Date

Type of Actions	Team meeting	Stakeholder integration	Implementation action	Grand Est Actions Global Progress
Discussion forum	0	2	2	13% Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

Grand Est IAMOT Report				2022																						
Primary	Assigned to	Status	Progress	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun
Integration of RRI cor	bernardini@grandenov.	●	▬																							
Encourage young girl	s.toussaint@grandenov.	●	▬																							
Integration of RRI in t	bernardini@grandenov.	●	▬																							
RRI criteria for public	a.steiner@grandenov.plu	●	▬																							
AI ethical Manifesto	a.steiner@grandenov.plu	●	▬																							
Sharing best practice	lucia.gonzalez@materali	●	▬																							
Company and acader	davy.monticolo@univ-lon	●	▬																							
UTTOPIA (technology	lucia.gonzalez@materali	●	▬																							
CE IAMOT Conferen	vincent.boly@univ-lorrain	●	▬																							
RRI awareness-raisin	lucia.gonzalez@materali	●	▬																							
Estival des Sciences	vincent.boly@univ-lorrain	●	▬																							
Survey on RRI practic	vincent.boly@univ-lorrain	●	▬																							

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/01/21 Starting date
 31/12/21 Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

D5.1 – Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/10/21 Starting date
30/06/22 Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

February 2022

Dashboard progress summary of actions in all 3 territories T5.1

Grand Est

Styria

Värmland

Grand Est Actions Global Progress

15%

Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

- Not yet started
- In Progress
- Finished

Styria Actions Global Progress

27%

Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

- Not yet started
- In Progress
- Finished

Värmland Actions Global Progress

27%

Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

- Not yet started
- In Progress
- Finished

Progress per action

Progress per action

Progress per action

D5.1 - Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/12/21 Starting date
30/09/22 Ending Date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

Grand Est IAMOT Report				2022												2023											
Primary	Assigned to	Status	Progress	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	D	
Integration of RRI concept in the future European Digital Innovation Hub	j.bernardini@grandenov	●	▬																								
Encourage young girls to digital sector	s.foussaint@grandenov vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																								
Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of Region Grand Est (2021-2027)	j.bernardini@grandenov	●	▬																								
RRI criteria for public funding	a.steiner@grandenov.pl	●	▬																								
AI ethical Manifesto	a.steiner@grandenov.pl	●	▬																								
Sharing best practices on information search tools	lucia.gonzalez@material	●	▬																								
Company and academic mutualized training: increasing digital skills through innovative educational workshops	davy.monticcolo@univ-lorraine.fr vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																								
UTTOPIA (technology transfer and technical orientation unit for prototyping and artificial intelligence) - innovation challenge	lucia.gonzalez@material	●	▬																								
CE IAMOT Conference: scientific/industrial/institutional meetings	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																								
RRI awareness-raising video	lucia.gonzalez@material	●	▬																								
Est'ival des Sciences Event	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																								
Survey on RRI practices in the FabLabs of the Grand Est Region	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																								

DS.1 - Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/01/21 Starting date
 31/12/21 Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

D5.1 – Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/10/21 Starting date
 30/06/22 Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

Värmland Gantt Report

Primary	Assigned to	Dead line date	Location	2021												2022											
				Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Apply the competence wheel	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	31/10/21	Digital																								
Use the competence	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	30/06/22	Digital																								
Mapping of solutions	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	31/03/22	Digital																								
Survey on the future	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	31/03/22	Digital																								
Design offers and ser	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	30/06/22	Digital																								
Digital Data Stewards	eamonn.mccallion@kau	30/06/22	Digital																								
Territorial attractivene	Angelica Jacobo, Eamon	30/06/22	Digital																								
Digitalisation and RRI	eamonn.mccallion@kau	31/05/22	Digital																								
Compilation of analyti	Anders Olsson, Angelica	30/06/22	Digital																								
Hiring of digital coordi	Anders Olsson, helen.vo	31/12/21	Digital																								
Digitalisation and S3	Anders Olsson, Angelica	31/03/22	Digital																								
Digitalisation and S3 -	Anders Olsson, Angelica	30/06/22	Digital																								
Interaction and excha	Cindy Bråtenfeldt, Eamo	31/01/22	Digital																								
Incubator exchange	Eamonn McCallion, Patri	30/06/22	Digital																								

March 2022

Dashboard progress summary of actions in all 3 territories T5.1

Grand Est

Styria

Värmland

Grand Est Actions Global Progress

27%

Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

- Not yet started
- In Progress
- Finished

Styria Actions Global Progress

37%

Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

- Not yet started
- In Progress
- Finished

Värmland Actions Global Progress

29%

Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

- Not yet started
- In Progress
- Finished
- Delayed

Progress per action

Progress per action

Progress per action

D5.1 - Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/12/21 Starting date
30/09/22 Ending Date

Progress per action

Grand Est DANTY Report				2022												2023											
Primary	Assigned to	Status	Progress	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec		
Integration of RRI concept in the future European Digital Innovation Hub	j.bernardini@grandenov.fr	In Progress	25%																								
Encourage young girls to digital sector	s.loussaint@grandenov.fr vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	Finished	100%																								
Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of Region Grand Est (2021-2027)	j.bernardini@grandenov.fr	In Progress	25%																								
RRI criteria for public funding	a.steiner@grandenov.pl	In Progress	50%																								
AI ethical Manifesto	a.steiner@grandenov.pl	Finished	75%																								
Sharing best practices on information search tools	lucia.gonzalez@materali.fr	Not yet started	0%																								
Company and academic mutualized training: increasing digital skills through innovative educational workshops	davy.montcosio@univ-lorraine.fr vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	In Progress	25%																								
UTTOPIA (technology transfer and technical orientation unit for prototyping and artificial intelligence) - innovation challenge	lucia.gonzalez@materali.fr	In Progress	25%																								
CE IAMOT Conference: scientific/industrial/institutional meetings	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	In Progress	25%																								
RRI awareness-raising video	lucia.gonzalez@materali.fr	Not yet started	0%																								
Est'ival des Sciences Event	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	Not yet started	0%																								
Survey on RRI practices in the FabLabs of the Grand Est Region	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	In Progress	25%																								

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/01/21 Starting date
 30/06/22 Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

T5.1 – Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/10/21 Starting date 30/06/22 Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

April 2022

Dashboard progress summary of actions in all 3 territories T5.1

Grand Est

Styria

Värmland

Grand Est Actions Global Progress

38%

Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

- Not yet started
- In Progress
- Finished

Styria Actions Global Progress

48%

Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

- Not yet started
- In Progress
- Finished

Värmland Actions Global Progress

48%

Average Actions Progress

Actions Status Distribution %

- Not yet started
- In Progress
- Finished
- Delayed

Progress per action

Progress per action

Progress per action

D5.1 - Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/12/21 Starting date
30/09/22 Ending Date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

Grand Est GANTT Report				2022												2023											
Primary	Assigned to	Status	Progress	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	
Integration of RRI concept in the future European Digital Innovation Hub	j.bernardini@grandenov.pl	●	▬	█	█	█	█																				
Encourage young girls to digital sector	s.loussaint@grandenov.pl vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬	█	█	█	█																				
Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of Region Grand Est (2021-2027)	j.bernardini@grandenov.pl	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
RRI criteria for public funding	a.steiner@grandenov.pl	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
AI ethical Manifesto	a.steiner@grandenov.pl	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Sharing best practices on information search tools	lucia.gonzalez@materali	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Company and academic mutualized training: increasing digital skills through innovative educational workshops	davy.monticello@univ-lorraine.fr vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
UTOPIA (technology transfer and technical orientation unit for prototyping and artificial intelligence) - innovation challenge	lucia.gonzalez@materali	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
CE IAMOT Conference: scientific/industrial/institutional meetings	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
RRI awareness-raising video	lucia.gonzalez@materali	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Est'val des Sciences Event	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Survey on RRI practices in the FabLabs of the Grand Est Region	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/01/21 Starting date
 30/06/22 Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

D5.1 - Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/10/21
Starting date

30/06/22
Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

Värmland Gantt Report

Primary	Assigned to	Deadline date	Location	2021												2022											
				Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Apply the competence wheel	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhi	31/10/21	Digital																								
Use the competence wheel	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhi	30/06/22	Digital																								
Mapping of solutions in use	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhi	31/03/22	Digital																								
Survey on the future needs	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhi	31/03/22	Digital																								
Design offers and services	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhi	30/06/22	Digital																								
Digital Data Stewardship Course	eamonn.mccallion@kau	30/06/22	Digital																								
Territorial attractiveness of Värmland	Angelica Jacobo, Eamon	30/06/22	Digital																								
Digitalisation and RRI in Leadership Training	eamonn.mccallion@kau	31/05/22	Digital																								
Compilation of analytical reports and studies	Anders Olsson, Angelica	30/06/22	Digital																								
Hiring of digital coordinator	Anders Olsson, helen.vc	31/12/21	Digital																								
Digitalisation and S3	Anders Olsson, Angelica	31/03/22	Digital																								
Digitalisation and S3 – expansion to Dalarna	Anders Olsson, Angelica	30/06/22	Digital																								
Interaction and exchange with other student Unions	Cindy Bråtenfeldt, Eamonn	31/01/22	Digital																								
Incubator exchange	Eamonn McCallion, Patri	30/06/22	Digital																								

DS.1 – Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

May 2022

Dashboard progress summary of actions in all 3 territories T5.1

Grand Est

Styria

Värmland

D5.1 - Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/01/22 Starting date
 30/06/22 Deadline date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

T5.1 – Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

Missing data
Starting date: 30/06/22
Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

Värmland GANTT Report				2021												2022											
Primary	Assigned to	Dead line date	Locatic	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Use the competence wheel	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	30/06/22	Digital																								
Mapping of solutions	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	31/03/22	Digital																								
Survey on the future needs	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	31/03/22	Digital																								
Design offers and services	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	30/06/22	Digital																								
Digital Data Stewardship Course	eamonn.mccallion@kau	30/06/22	Digital																								
Territorial attractiveness of Värmland	Angelica Jacobo, Eamon	30/06/22	Digital																								
Digitalisation and RRI in Leadership Training	eamonn.mccallion@kau	31/05/22	Digital																								
Compilation of analytical reports and studies	Anders Olsson, Angelica	30/06/22	Digital																								
Hiring of digital coordinator	Anders Olsson, helen.v	31/12/21	Digital																								
Digitalisation and S3	Anders Olsson, Angelica	31/03/22	Digital																								
Digitalisation and S3 – expansion to Dalarna	Anders Olsson, Angelica	30/06/22	Digital																								
Incubator exchange	Eamonn McCallion, Patri	30/06/22	Digital																								

June 2022

Dashboard progress summary of actions in all 3 territories T5.1

D5.1 - Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/12/21 Starting date
30/09/22 Ending Date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

Grand Est GANTT Report				2021												2022												
Primary	Assigned to	Status	Progress	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Integration of RRI concept in the future European Digital Innovation Hub	jj.bernardini@grandenov.	●	▬																									
Encourage young girls to digital sector	s.toussaint@grandenov. vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																									
Integration of RRI in the Smart Specialisation Strategy of Region Grand Est (2021-2027)	jj.bernardini@grandenov.	●	▬																									
RRI criteria for public funding	a.steiner@grandenov.plu	●	▬																									
AI ethical Manifesto	a.steiner@grandenov.plu	●	▬																									
Sharing best practices on information search tools	lucia.gonzalez@materali	●	▬																									
Company and academic mutualized training: increasing digital skills through innovative educational workshops	davy.monticolo@univ-lorraine.fr vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																									
UTTOPIA (technology transfer and technical orientation unit for prototyping and artificial intelligence) - innovation challenge	lucia.gonzalez@materali	●	▬																									
CE IAMOT Conference: scientific/industrial/institutional meetings	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																									
RRI awareness-raising video	lucia.gonzalez@materali	●	▬																									
Est'ival des Sciences Event	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																									
Survey on RRI practices in the FabLabs of the Grand Est Region	vincent.boly@univ-lorraine.fr	●	▬																									

DS.1 - Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

01/01/22 Starting date
 30/06/22 Deadline date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

Styria GANTT Report			2021												2022												
Primary	Assigned to	Status	Progre	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Blackout precautions	brigitte.kriszt@unileoben	●																									
Females fit for digitali	brigitte.kriszt@unileoben	●																									
Fit4MINT	brigitte.kriszt@unileoben	●																									
Exchange of Student	brigitte.kriszt@unileoben	●																									
Digi@Lab	brigitte.kriszt@unileoben	●																									
Awareness of the Sty	brigitte.kriszt@unileoben	●																									
Concept developmen	franz.edler@unternehme	●																									
Training on digital ma	franz.edler@unternehme	●																									
Incubator exchange fi	franz.edler@unternehme	●																									
Cross Regional Even	brigitte.kriszt@unileoben	●																									
Plan Scan & Shop - e	erich.weber@marketing-	●																									
Job platform for munii	erich.weber@marketing-	●																									

D5.1 - Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach

Dashboard progress summary of actions in T5.1

Missing data Starting date
30/06/22 Dead line date

Actions Status Distribution %

Actions Status Distribution Quantity

Progress per action

Värmland GANTT Report				2021												2022											
Primary	Assigned to	Dead line date	Location	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Apply the competence	Mikael Holmgren, Per Mj	31/12/21	Digital																								
Use the competence	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	30/06/22	Digital																								
Mapping of solutions	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	31/03/22	Digital																								
Survey on the future	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	31/03/22	Digital																								
Design offers and ser	Mikael Holmgren, p.myhr	31/12/22	Digital																								
Digital Data Stewards	eamonn.mccallion@kau	30/09/22	Digital																								
Territorial attractiveness	Angelica Jacobo, Eamon	31/12/22	Digital																								
Digitalisation and RRI	eamonn.mccallion@kau	30/09/22	Digital																								
Compilation of analyt	Anders Olsson, Angelica	30/06/22	Digital																								
Hiring of digital coordi	Anders Olsson, helen,vo	31/12/21	Digital																								
Digitalisation and S3	Anders Olsson, Angelica	31/03/22	Digital																								
Digitalisation and S3	Anders Olsson, Angelica	30/06/22	Digital																								
Incubator exchange	Eamonn McCallion, Patri	30/06/22	Digital																								

